

Enhancing Software maintainability and Software quality by detecting and combating Code Smells in Object Oriented Programming

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ABSTRACT

Code Smells are usually the situations that arise because of bad programming practices or poorly written program code. They are not considered as errors but are technically incorrect implementations. These can arise due to various strategies and concepts that are adopted to code or sometimes due to the logic that is being used. A Java code is no way exception to presence of Code Smells. Infact, it is more susceptible and vulnerable to Code Smells than many other languages. In this paper, various Code Smells that are seen in in Object Oriented Programming with special reference to Java Programming language are presented and also few tools and techniques to resolve them are discussed. It is also discussed as to whether Software maintainability and Software quality are affected by the presence of Code Smells in Java. This research paper consists of analysis and presentation of information collected from various scholarly articles and web articles. Based on the study and analysis, it is found that Software maintenance becomes difficult and Software quality also deteriorates to some extent because of the presence of Code Smells in a Software. Also Code smells are likely to affect the speed of execution and appearance of the code.

Keywords: Code Smells, Java, Software quality, Software maintainability, Types of Code Smell, Refactoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality of Code is a metric always used by the Software Development community. Reusability of code is something which the community looks for quite often on a long term basis. On the contrary, low quality code that can solve a problem at the given moment of time only is far from long term consequences. Code Smells is also one such feature of Coding which affects the long term consequences rather than the current situation or scenario. It is the structure of the code, which otherwise is absolutely right and correct, has some means of shortcut approach to solve a given problem [9]. High Software Quality is also expected for a successful software product. Hence the development team should constantly practice and look for the presence of

Code Smells in the project. This is very much required for the long term maintenance of the software system too.

In this paper, Section 2 contains a brief literature review on Code Smells and its impact on Software Quality and Maintenance. Next section presents the various types of Code Smells especially in Java. In Section 4, various tools and techniques used to detect Code Smells is discussed. Section 5 throws light on the overall Software Quality issues with Code Smells and Section 6 talks about the Software Maintenance issues with the presence of Code Smells in Code. Section 7 contains the conclusion and future work that can be carried out with Code Smells.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There has been a lot of research that has gone into Code Smells over the years in almost all the languages. For our study, we have chosen few relevant papers which are summarised as follows:

In their paper [1], the authors present a different view of code quality by investigating whether finding of code smells can contribute to automatic software inspection and also on a general method for building a software inspection tool that can detect code smells. A tool by name jCOSMO which is a prototype code smell browser was developed here.

In their paper [2], the authors have discussed about the effects of eliminating any kind of code smell on software quality metrics. They have tried to make a note on the factors that influence on deciding which code smells have to be removed first when there are many such. They have also tried to find out if there exists any dependencies between same code smells across various systems or applications.

In [3] the authors have tried to show a relationship between design patterns and code smells. To add on, they have analysed around nine design patterns along with seven code smells in two open source Java applications. It is observed that the classes involved in design patterns show less of code smells than other classes.

Di Nucci, D., et al [4] have chosen machine learning models to detect Code Smells. Here the authors build datasets with one or more types of code smell. They have also taken care to see that smelly and non smelly instances are equally distributed in the given dataset. Hence they prove that detecting code smells using Machine learning techniques is quite relevant.

3. CATEGORIES OF CODE SMELLS IN JAVA

Most developers focus specifically on the feature to be delivered. It takes practice and experience for a developer to detect and fix code smells that his code might raise. There are more than a hundred different code smells that can occur. The most commonly occurring in a typical development environment are being explored here. Based on their occurrence, we can classify them into two major categories: Within Classes and Between Classes. It is important for any developer to be aware of the various types of code smells that can be caused, especially in a Java Class [5].

3.1 Code Smells Within Classes:

In this section, the most common Code Smells that occur within Classes are discussed. This is the most basic category since most developers need to focus on the class that they are working with.

3.1.1 Comments:

Comments are simple statements typically with the explanation of the code at any particular level. These are ignored by the compiler and are purely written only to make the code be documented well. There is a fine line between writing comments that are simple and helpful in explaining the 'why' and not the 'what'. Keeping in mind that writing comments are only for the humans who are reading it to understand and it does nothing to the machine, one should be able to refactor the code in such a way that the comments are not needed. It is expected that the code that is written should be self-documenting and should be able to reveal the intention of that code. In case a detailed comment is required to explain a complex code then it must be converted into separate modules that divide the complex code into multiple simple sub-modules. In short, it is expected to write code that is easily understandable by any programmer who reads it without having to explain each part with a comment.

3.1.2 Long Method:

Normally methods or functions are written as small blocks of code that can be called again. If those methods are very long or unnecessarily lengthy, that also attributes to Code Smells. Methods containing too many lines of code are normally not entertained. It must be within 25 lines of code is the expected limit. If it has to exceed this count, it is expected to refactor this method. This process can be done using some simple refactoring techniques such as expression to subexpression, complex natured codes into smaller and simpler blocks of code etc. In other words, a shorter method is easy to read and understand, more importantly, easier to troubleshoot. Refactoring lengthy methods into smaller methods whenever possible needs to be done.

3.1.3 Long Parameter List:

Parameters are input given to methods to process. These parameters can be 0 or more. As the number of parameters increases for a method, it becomes that much complicated to test and debug. So, any method that takes more than 4 parameters can be considered to raise a Code Smell. To fix this particular code smell one needs to read the values. If that's the output of another method, it can be passed it as a method rather than as a parameter to get a shorter code that's more readable. Limit the number of parameters required for a given method, or use objects to merge parameters.

3.1.4 Duplicate Code:

Sometimes it is observed that the same code is getting repeated in a program for various purposes. When a piece of code is occurring more than once in the same class it is that is also a Code Smell. To fix this, when there is repeated occurrences, merge them into a method of the class. The extract method of refactoring to fix this code smell can be used. If the repeated code is found in a constructor, the pull-up constructor body can be applied and the others that help in refactoring this issue are the Form Template method, Pull-up field, Substitute algorithm and so on. Repeated code is a huge code smell and must be avoided wherever it is possible.

3.1.5 Dead Code:

Code that is not used throughout the program execution is called Dead Code. For example, a method that is written and never being called, a Condition that will never occur, etc. One must always be able to identify blocks of code that are never used or never will be called and remove them to avoid unnecessary Code smells. Also care should be taken to remove the parameters

that are passed to this dead code which will never be called to improve our code and to make it simpler and easier.

3.1.6 Large Classes:

A class is normally comprised of variables and methods and these classes start small and grow throughout development. It results in a class that has too many lines of codes or too many methods or simply too many fields in it and starts to become a Code Smell. If it is possible, one needs to divide this large class into smaller subclasses to avoid code smells. To fix this code smell, one needs to use refactoring techniques such as extract class, extract subclass, extract interface, duplicate observed data, etc.

3.1.7 Conditional Complexity:

When a program has a lot of conditional statements that need to check for various complex conditions, it may be considered as a Code Smell. Care should be taken to pay particular attention to blocks that tend to grow or change significantly over time, especially for large conditional logic blocks. Considering an alternative object-oriented approach such as decorators is a good choice.

3.1.8 Temporary Field:

While using an object that carries multiple fields in it, some fields are very rarely used and they normally act as a Temporary Field that raises code smells. So, one needs to be aware of objects that contain many optional or unnecessary fields. If an object is passed as a parameter to a method, one needs to make sure that everything is being used without just selecting a single field from it [6].

3.2 Code Smells Between Classes:

In this section, the most common Code Smells that occur between Classes is discussed. The most common and repeating ones in this category are discussed below

3.2.1 Data Classes:

Data Classes are classes that store only data and has no methods in them. This class has no functionality. They cannot work independently on the data they have. A Class must contain both data and methods. Using global or local variables is a solution to avoid this Code Smell. If the data class contains public data, it can be hidden using the encapsulation method. A Few other refactoring techniques to address this is the Move, Extract, and Remove methods. In simple terms, the Class must contain data and methods that operate on that data.

3.2.2 Data Clumps:

Data Clumps arise in code because similar data can belong to the same class. Consider using a superclass. For example, parameters to connect to a database. This chunk should be merged into a new class. If one is constructing a field from a data class that is repeating data, an extract class technique can be used to move the field to the class or create a class. Other refactoring techniques for dealing with this Code Smell are: Introducing parameter objects, Preserving whole objects, etc. In Short, If one sees that the same data keeps occurring together, then it is to be noted that they probably belong together. In that case merging relevant data into a larger class has to be done.

3.2.3 Alternative Classes with Different Interfaces:

While working on an Enterprise level project, there might be a chance that two classes created by two different people might look different on the outside but stay very similar on the inside. If both classes are similar inside, they can be changed so as to share a common interface. For example, a programmer who created one of the classes may not be aware that a similar class already exists or that another programmer on the team has created it. The refactoring methods to handle this are the Rename Method, Move, Add Parameter, and Parameterize Method.

3.2.4 Refused Bequest:

Inheritance is a concept that allows the developer to reuse the functionalities of the parent in the child class. If a Base Class is inherited and has not utilized any of its functionalities then the concept of Inheritance is not needed there and hence a Code Smell occurs. For example, suppose that there is a class called a body, then human class and animal class can inherit from the body class. A car also has a body, but if it is inherited then it doesn't make sense. Refactoring method to deal with this type of Code Smells are Delegate inheritance, Replace delegate, extract superclass, etc.

3.2.5 Lazy Class:

A Class that doesn't contribute much to the working or functionality of the project can be termed as a Lazy Class. These Classes can cost both time and money and should be removed. For example, a class designed to work perfectly may be wasted after some refactoring and code changes, or it may be rarely used. If there are classes that are not doing enough, then we must consider removing them or combine them with another class. Inline classes can be used and shrink hierarchies to make the code size smaller and easier to understand and maintain.

3.2.6 Shotgun Surgery:

This term comes because of a fact that Multiple shots occur in a single fire from a shotgun. Similarly, if changing code in a class affects several related classes then it also raises a Code Smell. This can happen after over-applying Divergent Changes and can be avoided by refactoring in such a way that the changes only affect that class. The Move Method and Move Field make it easier to maintain code and reduce duplication.

3.2.7 Incomplete Library Class:

In a scenario where one needs a method that is required from a library but is not available, then that can be called as an Incomplete Library class. If one does not want or could not modify the library to include that missing method, then this method will be attached to another class altogether. So to fix this code smell in which one is not able to modify the library, he or she must consider isolating that method.

3.2.8 Indecent Exposure:

While programming some tend to use the public access modifiers a lot without any specific purpose, which exposes those data without any restriction. Hence one needs to be very much aware of classes that unnecessarily expose their internals. To avoid this Code Smell, actively refactoring classes to minimize the exposed surface has to be done. There must be a valid and compelling reason for each item that is made public. Otherwise consider encapsulating it.

4. TOOLS USED TO COMBAT CODE SMELLS

There are various detection techniques used in detecting Code Smells and they are generally based on the calculation of specific combinations of metric sets, standard object-oriented

metrics, or metric that is temporarily defined for simple detection purposes. It is indeed a complex problem because we have to define a threshold value for these metrics which can be sometimes very particular to a Code Smell. There are a variety of Code Smell Detection tools available for download and use such as Borland Together, CCFinder (CCFinderX), Checkstyle, Code Bad Smell Detector, Colligens, ConcernReCS, ConQAT, DECKARD, DuDe, Gendarme, inCode, inFusion, IntelliJ IDEA, iPlasma, Java Clone Detector (JCD), jCosmo, JDeodorant, NiCad, NosePrints, PMD, PoSDef, SDMetrics, SpIRIT (JSpIRIT), Stench Blossom, SYMake, TrueRefactor, Understand, Wrangler and lot more [7].

5. SOFTWARE QUALITY ISSUES WITH CODE SMELLS

There are different approaches available to detect Code Smells. Some developers and development team review the code and check for Code Smells at the end of every phase of development cycle. On the other hand, Code Smells can also be reviewed at the end of the entire Software development life cycle. Code Smells is one of the proven reasons towards determining Software Quality. Software Inspection is a step which is performed to inspect the given code. This is a solution for improving Software quality [1]. This process can be a manual process or an automated process. Nevertheless, the result is the same and is used to detect Code Smells. A lot of research has been conducted over the years to find out whether detection of Code Smells really affect the overall Software quality. It is interesting to note that no research so far has given a definite result or a uniform result in terms of Software quality. Different types of Code Smells have shown different effects on various quality attributes [8]. In other words, every Code Smell shows unique results on Software Quality issue and do not affect the Software Quality equally.

6. SOFTWARE MAINTENANCE ISSUES WITH CODE SMELLS

Code Smells have mixed effect on Software Maintenance. Different Code Smells show different effects on maintenance. It is proved that Code Smell Duplicated code is very much beneficial. Some of them actually do not need refactoring [9]. One more research states that all of the defective code cannot be linked with duplicated code. In fact the code that is replicated less frequently is more error-prone than the code that is replicated more frequently [10]. When it comes to God Class, it is observed that an implementation without a God Class is complete, accurate and consistent than a design with a God Class [11]. Presence of Code Smells can be taken as a promising indicator of problematic files during Software maintenance. Some of the Code Smells can also affect from a practical maintenance perspective [12]

7. LIMITATION AND CONCLUSION

The study here is limited to effect on Quality and maintenance with respect to single Code Smells. Future Work on combinations of various code smells and their effects on Software Quality and Maintenance issues can be done. Also quantification of Quality or Maintenance aspect is not considered in this paper. Nevertheless, it is understood that Software Quality is not uniformly affected due to the presence of Code Smells. Some of them show a positive effect whereas some show a negative effect. Code Smells also have shown mixed implications on Software Maintenance.

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